

A NOVEL DATA SECURE MODEL FOR INTERNET OF HEALTH THINGS WITH A NEW LIGHTWEIGHT CRYPTOGRAPHY ALGORITHM AND STEGANOGRAPHY TECHNIQUE

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ABSTRACT

Ensuring the security of data in Internet of Things (IoT) based healthcare systems (HS) presents considerable challenges due to the limitations of traditional embedding methods and cryptography techniques, leading to more memory consumption, more execution time, less security, inadequate payload capacity, and performance inefficiencies. To address these issues, the Bernoulli Fish-based Stego Algorithm (BFBSA) is introduced as an innovative solution. Specifically designed for IoT healthcare data, this algorithm is validated through the encryption and embedding of healthcare data. The process involves initializing IoT healthcare data, encrypting it using the BFBSA algorithm, and embedding the encrypted data within steganographic images. Performance analysis is conducted using key metrics such as payload capacity, encryption time, memory usage, PSNR, and MSE. Comparative analysis with existing approaches highlights the BFBSA model's efficiency and its effectiveness in ensuring secure and optimized data management in IoT healthcare environments.

Keywords: *IoT Healthcare, Encryption, Embedding Image, Data Security, Crypto Algorithm.*

1. INTRODUCTION

The IoT is the connected network. It is similar to vision in which, on the network, every object can be identified uniquely [1]. In this, the objects are living beings like animals or humans, and non-living entities in the world [2]. The IoT could be a network that is connected to devices to collect and share data [3]. The IoT contains of things which are interconnected in the cities, houses, roads, and vehicles, which track the user's behavior and use collected data for several services [4]. It will be part of the everyday life. IoT devices will transform many features of industrial and home automation components. IoT products similar to internet-enabled appliances are progressing toward presenting energy-efficient homes and security [5]. From the private user point of view, the IoT introduction is the most evident effect that will be visible in both the domestic and working fields [6]. The IoT consists of four layers: physical, network, perception, and application [7]. The physical layer refers to the hardware, which includes other gadgets and smart appliances. The network layer includes the network coverage

components and communication [8]. The perception layer relates to devices and sensors communicating with other objects. The application layer refers to standard practices like smart transport, smart cities, and intelligent homes [9]. Healthcare on the Internet of Things is growing rapidly, and access to treatment is improving. The quality of health care has also increased, and the cost has been reduced [10]. Well-being is integrated based on an individual's unique behavioral, social, biological, and cultural characteristics. Personalized healthcare refers to the support and healthcare given to patient [11]. It permits every individual to get the healthcare at the right time, which improves the outcome and satisfaction, making it cost-effective healthcare.

The Internet of Things gives assurance to manage care services and maintain every person's digital identity [12]. In IoT healthcare, different equipment is used to communicate [13]. The IoT classification is based on the healthcare personalization system, which includes remote monitoring and care [14]. The Internet of Things addresses health issues and offers a world of cloud-based

applications, connected devices and services, cooperation mechanisms with diversity, and enables large data analytics for getting information and objective data, and decision-making is well grounded [15]. The main problem is that, for patients living in remote areas, for those who are in hospitals for treatments, doctors are unavailable in critical conditions [16].

Nowadays, the IoT health ecosystem is organized on wireless devices that are directly connected to collect important information [17]. Nowadays, with the implementation of new approaches for the health monitoring system by IoT devices, these issues may be significantly alleviated [18]. The IoT in healthcare is a huge environment. The connected overall health care tools and healthcare data form a more integrated system, which is used for (IoHT) Internet of Healthcare Things [19].

1.1. Current Applications of Internet of Things (IoT)

1.1.1. An IoT-based health monitoring system (HMS) for remote patients enables continual monitoring of essential health indicators such as blood pressure, body temperature, heart rate, ECG, and oxygen saturation. These systems employ sensors attached to the patient's body to gather medical information, which is then sent to a cloud-based system like ThingSpeak using communication modules (such as the ESP8266 Wi-Fi module) and microcontrollers (like the Arduino UNO).

Doctors and caregivers can access this data remotely using online or mobile applications, allowing them to follow the patient's status without having to visit the hospital. Alerts may be created automatically when any health parameter reaches a critical level, allowing for quick response. This method is especially useful in rural or underdeveloped regions, where access to medical professionals is restricted, because it improves healthcare quality while lowering expenses and travel difficulties.

The proposed system architecture employs multiple sensors interfaced with an Arduino UNO microcontroller. The ESP8266 Wi-Fi module facilitates wireless communication to transmit real-time data to the ThingSpeak cloud platform. The monitored parameters include:

Body Temperature (LM35 Sensor): The output voltage of the high-precision integrated-circuit LM35 temperature sensor is proportional to the temperature measured in degrees Celsius. It is common for its excellent accuracy, minimal power consumption, and simplicity of integration with microcontrollers. The sensor provides temperature readings in real-time, which are crucial for monitoring fever or hypothermia.

Heart Rate (Pulse Sensor): This sensor is designed to identify the heartbeat by measuring the change in blood volume through the skin. It uses photo plethysmography (PPG) technology, which involves emitting light through the skin and measuring the amount reflected. The pulse sensor is efficient in detecting beats per minute (BPM) with high precision, making it ideal for monitoring cardiac activity.

ECG (Electrocardiogram Module): The ECG module detects electrical impulses produced by the heart using electrodes implanted on the skin. It contains useful information on the heart's rhythm, pace, and electrical activity. The ECG sensor outputs graphical data, which can be visualized and analyzed for detecting abnormalities such as arrhythmias and ischemia, enlarged chambers and defects in heart.

Blood Pressure (Blood Pressure Sensor): Blood pressure monitoring is achieved utilizing a non-invasive device capable of detecting systolic and diastolic pressure. Accurate measurement of blood pressure is essential for diagnosing hypertension and monitoring cardiovascular health. This sensor operates by using the oscillometric method, which involves detecting changes in artery wall pressure.

Oxygen Saturation (SpO₂ - Pulse Oximeter Sensor): The pulse oximeter device measures the pulse rate and blood oxygen saturation using a non-intrusive optical method. It functions by emitting light wavelengths through a body part, such as a fingertip, and detecting the amount of light absorbed by oxygenated and deoxygenated blood. Continuous monitoring of SpO₂ is critical for detecting respiratory issues and ensuring adequate oxygen supply.

Figure 1: IOT Health monitoring system

Figure 2: Arduino controller

Figure 3: ECG Biomedical connector

Figure 4: ESP8266 module

The Arduino UNO analyzes sensor data and delivers it to the ThingSpeak cloud via the ESP8266 modules. Data visualization and analysis are performed using graphical tools provided by ThingSpeak, enabling remote monitoring and timely decision-making.

1.1.2. Security of Data in IoT Health Monitoring Systems

In IoT-based HMS, data security is crucial because sensitive patient information is collected, transmitted, and stored across connected devices and cloud platforms. Protecting this data secures its security, integrity, and accessibility, and also prevents unauthorized use, breaches, or tampering.

1.1.3. Smart Home Using Internet of Things (IoT)

IoT technology is used in smart homes to link different systems and devices to the web, including lighting, thermostats, appliances, and entertainment systems. Smartphones, voice assistants (such as Alexa or Google Assistant), or programmed schedules can be used to manage these devices remotely and interact with others. IoT enables convenience, energy efficiency, and personalized living experiences by allowing users to monitor and manage their home environment in real-time, whether they are at home or away.

1.1.4. Smart Home Security Using Internet of Things (IoT)

Smart home security (SHS) with IoT involves integrating devices like smart cameras, motion sensors, door locks, window sensors, and alarm systems into a connected network. These devices can detect unusual activity, send instant alerts to homeowners, and even allow live video streaming through mobile apps. IoT-based

security systems can automate responses such as locking doors, sounding alarms, or notifying authorities, enhancing both safety and peace of mind. Advanced features may include facial recognition, geo-fencing, and AI-based threat detection.

1.1.5. IOT based Health care system:Ensuring the security of data in IoT-based Health care System presents considerable challenges due to the limitations of traditional embedding methods and cryptography techniques, leading to more memory consumption, more execution time, less security, inadequate payload capacity, and performance inefficiencies. To address these issues, the Bernoulli Fish-based Stego Algorithm (BFBSA) is introduced as an innovative solution BFBSA provides security for data in IOT network from different security threats such as cyber reconnaissance, brute force attack, and tracking

1.2. The developed work's primary contribution is outlined below:

Initially, the IoT health care data is considered as the input for this work.

Consequently, a new BFBSA was developed to encrypt the data and utilize image steganography for incorporating the encrypted data into the image.

Primarily, the input data was encrypted into a secret code to make the data confidential.

Then, the encrypted data was hidden in the image using image steganography with the help of BFBSA.

Finally, the performance of a lightweight cryptography algorithm is measured, and the parameters payload capacity, encryption time, memory consumption, MSE, and PSNR were measured.

The suggested model's structure is as follows: A comprehensive review of existing studies is given in Section 2, along with a thorough examination of pertinent articles. Section 3 describes the chosen approach and specifies the current process. In Section 4, this suggested approach is explained in detail. A thorough description of the experimental investigations that were conducted is given in Section 5. Finally, Section 6 concludes the study by identifying potential ways for future study and summarizing important findings.

2. RELATED WORKS

A few recent related studies are explained as follows,

Adel et al. [21] secured the effective

pictures using an image steganography technique based on BESOPS-CE. Initializes the Bald Eagle Search (BES) method for embedding in order to choose the pixel spots efficiently. Utilize the chaotic method of encryption to secure the private images; the distant images are included in the selected pixel locations. At last, this method carried out the embedding and extraction processes. Compared to the other approaches, the BESOPS-CE framework has achieved a more significant PSNR value on each test image. The scale image dataset from the actual time environment is expanded.

Ditta *et al.* [22] proposed a novel algorithm combined with steganography and cryptography for securing confidential data and improving capacity. The proposed algorithm used a linguistic steganography model to hide the data in Arabic text. Before the critical data was hidden, the secret data was encrypted using the bit inversion algorithm. This algorithm provides high data security. Using the linguistic steganography algorithm to identify personal data is more challenging because it is less redundant. The size-effective algorithm could be more efficient in reducing the text size.

Fatiha *et al.* [23] introduced a scheme of IoT for audio steganography for embedding the audio signal to produce a stego signal. Its foundation is the area-locating method for embedding high-frequency data, which increases the payload's capacity. Using acoustic signals and the many voice-activated devices, steganography protects data while broadening its application range for IoT applications. More considerable energies and shorter frequencies are given priority for data concealment utilizing the signal's spectral features. This technique uses a larger number of gadgets and a higher amount of IoT communication to secure data.

Sachin *et al.* [24] suggested a slap swam optimization method (SSOA) to increase the payload capacity using different parameters, based on the adaptive function of integration. This technique makes effective use of localized blocks and edges by applying the SSOA algorithm. To enhance picture quality, we also employed a fuzzy neural network system fused with the back propagation learning technique. High security is used to transport the Stego pictures to their destination. This method shows the best outcomes in image quality, security,

and payload capacity.

Almomani *et al.* [25] presented an integrated crypto steganography framework for high-resolution image frame data hiding. The most minor bit and a sophisticated encryption algorithm are the basis of this steganography technique. Here, we used various ransom instances and resolutions of high-frequency video coding (HFVC) frames for the experiments. Randomly performs the embedding process, reducing the possibility of attack. The hybrid crypto steganography method proves excellent efficiency. Here, the various multimedia files are not utilized because of the limited data capacity.

3. PROBLEM STATEMENT

The current research in IOT data security results in adversely affecting other performance metrics of the network, such as throughput and packet delivery ratio (PDR), and also gives poor results in terms of data integrity, security, and requires large memory and processors. Still, there is scope for improvement in the existing protocols; thus, a lightweight cryptographic algorithm for the security of data in the IoT is required. In this research, a lightweight cryptographic algorithm with a steganography technique is proposed. This is an effective approach that guarantees data security. The lightweight cryptography algorithm was developed to be implemented for encryption and a better steganography technique for embedding IoT health care data, resulting in good performance.

4. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

A novel Bernoulli Fish-based Stego Algorithm (BFBSA) was introduced in this study for the IoT healthcare environment. Hence, this proposed BFBSA is validated by processing the encryption and embedding the healthcare data. Before encrypting the data, initialize the healthcare data. Then, utilize the suggested technique to encrypt the provided healthcare data.

Figure 5: Proposed architecture: BFBSA

Finally, the encrypted image data was hidden in Stego images, and the performance of the process was measured with the following metrics: payload capacity, encryption time, memory consumption, PSNR, and MSE. The method of the suggested architecture is described in Figure 1.

4.1. Process of the BFBSA Model

The security design is composed of a Bernoulli distribution, a cryptography algorithm, and a steganography technique. The IoT healthcare dataset is obtained and integrated into the suggested design to validate it. The data initializations defined in Eqn. (1)

$$H_d = \{I_1, I_2, \dots, I_n\} \quad (1)$$

Here, H_d represents the input dataset, the input images are indicated as I , and n denotes the number of images gathered.

4.1.1. Data Preprocessing

Before encryption, the healthcare image data is preprocessed. This step may include data compression, noise reduction, and data format adjustments to ensure the data is in a suitable form for encryption. The supplied dataset's noise characteristics are removed using Eqn. (2).

$$P_h = H_d + \lambda(l, m) \times [l - m] \quad (2)$$

Here, the noise filtering variable λ indicates the tracking variable, l defines the input characteristics, and m represents the noisy features. Hence, in the preprocessing, the noisy features are eliminated.

4.1.2 Encryption

The sender and receiver establish a mutually agreed-upon secure key for deployment within the Bernoulli Fish-Based Stego Algorithm (BFBSA) encryption method. Following this agreement, the sender selects an appropriate cover image to convey the secret message. Subsequently, the sender encodes the confidential data using the shared key and the BFBSA algorithm. Using the Bernoulli distribution, the sender chooses particular bits from the encrypted secret data to embed within the cover image. The distinctive image bit stream is divided into blocks of the required length in the BFBSA method. The development of a key initiates the encryption process. The data is then encrypted using the key. The bit widths of the controlling variables linked to the input data blocks have an impact on the key generation. The BFBSA

technique is used to encrypt the frames, and the created keys are obtained following the key generation process.

Figure 6: BFBSA processing round

Pseudo-code of Algorithm 1

```

BEGIN
  DEFINE S-BOX (256 predefined values)
  DEFINE NUMBER OF ROUNDS = 10
  FUNCTION Left Rotate(value, n):
    RETURN (value << n) OR (value >> (32 -
n)) AND 0xFFFFFFFF
  FUNCTION Generate Round Keys (key_high,
key_mid, key_low):
    INITIALIZE round_keys as an empty list
    FOR i FROM 0 TO ROUNDS-1 DO:
      rotated_high = Left Rotate (key_high, i)
      rotated_mid = Left Rotate (key_mid, i)
      rotated_low = Left Rotate (key_low, i)
      round_keys[i] = rotated_high XOR
rotated_mid XOR rotated_low
    RETURN round_keys
  FUNCTION Substitute(value):
    s_index = value MOD 128 // Get index into
S-Box
    RETURN S-BOX[s_index]
  FUNCTION Light weight Encrypt (left, right,
round_keys):
    FOR i FROM 0 TO ROUNDS-1 DO:
      shifted_left = Left Rotate (left, 3) XOR
round_keys[i]
      substituted = Substitute(shifted_left)
      temp = right
      right = substituted XOR temp
      left = temp
    RETURN left, right
  FUNCTION Main():
    SET left = 0x01234567
    SET right = 0x89abcdef
    SET key_high = 0xAABBCCDD
    SET key_mid = 0xEEFF0011
    SET key_low = 0x22334455
    CALL Generate Round Keys(key_high,

```

```

key_mid, key_low) → round_keys
  START TIMER
  CALL Light weight Encrypt (left, right,
round_keys) → (left, right)
  STOP TIMER
  COMPUTE execution_time_ms =
(end_time - start_time) * 1000
  PRINT "Encrypted data: Left =", left (hex
format), "Right =", right (hex format)
  PRINT "Execution time:",
execution_time_ms, "ms"
  CALL Main()
END

```

Explanation of the Pseudo-code:

1. Key Schedule Generation:

The 96-bit key is split into three 32-bit parts. Each part is left-rotated based on the round number. The rotated parts are XORed to generate round keys.

2. Encryption Process:

The plaintext is divided into two 32-bit halves (left and right). For each round, the left part is rotated and XORed with the round key. The result is substituted using a simplified S-Box. The right part is XORed with the substituted value. The left and right parts are updated accordingly. After 10 rounds, the final encrypted values are returned.

3. Execution Time Measurement:

The encryption time is measured in milliseconds and printed.

4.1.3. Key generation procedure of the BFBSA algorithm

1. The Master Key is randomly generated
 2. The Master Key is split into three 32-bit Parts:
 3. N-bit Left Rotation is applied to each 32-bit Part, where n is the round number
 4. Combine the Rotated values by performing the XOR operation to form the Round Sub key
 5. Same procedure followed for every round
- Example:

In BFBSA, the Block size is 64 bits, the key size is 96 bits, and the number of rounds taken is 10. Key Generation procedure with example to generate 10, 32-bit keys from 96-bit master key. The Master key of 96 bits is a randomly generated hexadecimal number

A 96-bit master key:

0x123456789ABCDEF012345678

4. Split the Master Key into Three 32-bit Parts:

Let's first split the 96-bit key into three 32-bit parts:

K1: The first 32 bits (bits 95-64)

K2: The middle 32 bits (bits 63-32)
 K3: The last 32 bits (bits 31-0)
 Calculation:
 K1 = 0x12345678 = 305419896 in decimal
 K2 = 0x9ABCDEF0 = 2596069104 in decimal
 K3 = 0x12345678 = 305419896 in decimal
 Apply a Left Rotation to Each 32-bit Part for Round 1:
 Since we're calculating the sub key for Round 1, we rotate each part by 1 bit to the left:
 K1rotated: Rotate K1 by 1 bit left.
 K1=0x12345678 becomes 0x2468ACF0
 K2rotated: Rotate K2 1 bit left.
 K2=0x9ABCDEF0 becomes 0x3579BDE1
 K3rotated: Rotate K3 by 1 bit left.
 K3=0x12345678 becomes 0x2468ACF0
 Combine the Rotated Parts to Form the Round 1 Sub key:
 Finally, combine the rotated values using XOR:
 Calculation:
 Sub key Round 1= K1rotated \oplus K2rotated \oplus K3rotated
 0x2468ACF0 \oplus 0x3579BDE1 \oplus 0x2468ACF0= 0x3579BDE1
 Result: Sub key for Round 1: 0x3579BDE1

4.1.4. Substitution Box(S-Box)

A S-Box with 256 entries is used for substitution
 S_BOX = [0xd1310ba6, 0x98dfb5ac,
 0x2ffd72db, 0xd01adfb7, 0xb8e1afed,
 0x6a267e96, 0xba7c9045, 0xf12c7f99,
 0x24a19947, 0xb3916cf7, 0x0801f2e2,
 0x858efc16, 0x636920d8, 0x71574e69,
 0xa458fea3, 0xf4933d7e,0x0d95748f,
 0x728eb658, 0x718bcd58, 0x82154aee,
 0x7b54a41d, 0xc25a59b5, 0x9c30d539,
 0x2af26013...]

This S-box is 256 values long, designed for memory efficiency while maintaining good non-linearity. It is derived from a subset of the Blowfish S-box values, preserving cryptographic properties like diffusion and confusion. Each value is a 32-bit integer (hex format), used for substitution during encryption. Compact & Efficient: Uses only 128 values instead of 1024, saving memory. Maintains Security: Retains the Blowfish design principles. Faster Lookups: Smaller table means faster access & substitution.

4.1.5. Comparison of Algorithms

Table 1: Comparison Table

Algorithm	Key Size	Block Size	Rounds	Execution Time (ms)	RAM Usage (KB)	Security Level
Proposed-BFBSA	96	64	10	1	1	High
AES-128	128	128	10	1.5	4	High
SPECK-96/96	96	96	26	1.5	1	High
SIMON-96/96	96	96	36	1.5	1	High
PRESENT-80	80	64	31	2.5	1	High
TEA (Tiny Encryption Algorithm)	128	64	32	3.5	2	High
HIGHT	128	64	32	1.5	1	High

4.1.6. Image steganography

Once encrypted, the data is hidden within steganographic images. It involves embedding the encrypted information into the pixels of an image using the BFBSA algorithm. Embedding the encrypted image data into stereo images consists of hiding the encrypted image data within another image. Using steganography ensures that sensitive healthcare data is concealed within seemingly innocuous images.

The goal of the suggested methodology is to improve data security in IoT healthcare images. It explains its technique through pseudo-code in Algorithm 2, delineating the step-by-step processes. A comprehensive algorithm elucidates the model's methodology, followed by executing Python code that adheres to these specified

procedures, enabling subsequent result verification. The workflow of the BFBSA model is depicted in Fig. 3.

Using effective methods establishes its suitability for ensuring secure transmission and storage of sensitive healthcare information in IoT environments. The payload capacity earned by our proposed technique is 1399105.125; when compared to the existing methods, it was improved. Future work could further enhance the BFBSA algorithm's effectiveness by exploring different encryption methods and optimization. Additionally, investigating the applicability of the BFBSA algorithm to other types of data, like video and text, would be a valuable area of research. Future research can focus on whether these methods are used in different IoT applications, such as smart home and industrial IoT. The

proposed algorithm is suitable for the security of IoT healthcare data. It may not be suitable for online transactions.

Figure 7: Flowchart of the BFBSA model

5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The proposed framework, the BFBSA, aims to secure IoT healthcare image data. Initially, datasets containing healthcare images are gathered and input into the technique. After the data initialization, the passing stage is conducted to eliminate noise. Subsequently, the image undergoes encryption using the Bernoulli fish algorithm. Additionally, embedding the encrypted image data into steganographic images entails concealing the encrypted image within another image. The parameters for implementation are detailed in Table 2.

Table 2: Execution parameters

Parameters	Type
Version	3.10
OS	Windows 10
Platform	Python
Dataset	IoT Healthcare image

5.1. Case Study:

The case study aimed to examine how the system was designed. The dataset is assembled and then added to the proposed framework, including the healthcare photographs. After gathering the image datasets, noise is removed through preprocessing, and the image is encrypted and embedded. The IoT healthcare

image data was collected from the standard site.

Table 3: Dataset description

Total: 5842	
Normal	1577
Pneumonia	4265
Training (80%):5216	
Normal	1341
Pneumonia	3875
Testing (20%):626	
Normal	236
Pneumonia	390

Table 3 describes the dataset details. There are 5842 occurrences in the dataset overall, of which 4265 have a pneumonia diagnosis, and 1577 are considered normal. Five thousand two hundred sixteen cases (80%) of the data are removed to train a classification model, essentially maintaining the original distribution of 1341 standard cases and 3875 pneumonia cases. The testing set consists of the remaining 20% (626 cases), with a notably more significant percentage of pneumonia (390) than typical (236), which may pose a challenge to the ability of the model to identify this class correctly.

Table 4: Sample encrypted and steganography image

Input image	Encrypted image	Steganography image

Embedding the encrypted image data into stereo images involves hiding the encrypted image data within another image. The encrypted and steganographic image is shown in Table 4. Memory consumption is the amount of computer memory used during the encryption and embedding processes. It is typically measured in bytes. Lower memory consumption indicates a more efficient algorithm.

5.2. Performance Analysis

A comparative analysis of the BFBSA model, which was developed with Python on the latest version of Windows 10, demonstrated its improved performance compared to other existing techniques. These include Medical Image Steganography Particle Swarm Optimization Algorithm (MISPSO) [26], Reversible Data Hiding based Histogram-Shifting (RDHHS) [27], Image Region

Decomposition (IRD) [28], High-Capacity Data Hiding Technique (HCDHT) [29], Blockchain-Based Biomedical Image Processing System (BBIPS) [30], Fingerprint-Based Authenticated Transmission (FAT) [31], Digital Color Image Encryption Approach (DCIEA) [32], Chaos-Based Image Encryption (CBIE) [33]. The developed BFBSA scheme was evaluated using several performance metrics.

5.2.1. Payload Capacity

Payload capacity (PC) quantifies the amount of data that can be effectively hidden in steganographic images. It is typically measured in bits per pixel (bpp). A higher payload capacity indicates that more data can be hidden in the image without significantly affecting quality. It is calculated by using the Eqn. (4).

$$PC = \frac{(Embedded\ Data\ Size)}{(image\ size)} \times 8 \tag{3}$$

Table 5: Payload performance

Methods	Payload capacity (bits)
MISPSO	1030000
HCDHT	1204192
BFBSA	1399105.125

Figure 8: Comparison of payload capacity

The proposed BFBSA model outperforms the other models in terms of payload capacity. It can handle the largest amount of data among all the methods compared. It outshines all these methods with an immensely superior payload capacity of 1399105. This striking difference positions the BFBSA model as exceptionally proficient in managing extensive volumes of data compared to the other models considered in this evaluation. The comparison of payload capacity is illustrated in Figure 8 and Table 5.

5.2.2. Encryption Time

Encryption time is the time, it takes to perform the encryption process on the healthcare image data. It is typically measured in seconds. A shorter encryption time indicates a more efficient algorithm.

Figure 9: Encryption time comparison

The BFBSA framework's encryption time was compared with other prominent techniques to validate its efficiency in encryption speed. As illustrated in Figure 4, established methods like BBIPS, FAT, and DCIEA exhibited considerable encryption durations of 12.45, 13.54, and 4.37 seconds, respectively. In stark contrast, the BFBSA framework achieved notably faster encryption, clocking in at a mere 3.02 seconds. This significant reduction in encryption time underscores the superior performance. The comparison of encryption time is shown in Figure 9.

5.2.3. PSNR (Peak Signal-to-Noise Ratio)

A measure called PSNR compares the resolution of the steganographic pictures to the actual medical pictures. Logarithmic measurement is used to determine the proportion of a signal's maximum power potential to its noise power. A greater PSNR shows that the embedded information has less impact on the level of detail and that the steganographic photo appears more akin to the original image. The formulation of PSNR is described in Eqn. (4).

$$PSNR = 10 * \log_{10} \left(\frac{255^2}{MSE} \right) \tag{4}$$

Figure 10: Comparison of PSNR

In the realm of PSNR metrics, the performance analysis unveils distinctive characteristics among various models. MISPSO exhibits a lower PSNR value of 44.06, respectively, indicating limitations in its signal reconstruction quality. While the IRD method shows a respectable PSNR of 49.27, the RDHHS model emerges as a top performer with a notable PSNR of 54.21, showcasing superior signal fidelity. Yet, standing out prominently is the proposed BFBSA model, showcasing an exceptional PSNR of 55.29. The proposed BFBSA model achieves the highest PSNR value, indicating its superior ability to preserve data quality during encryption. The comparison of PSNR is shown in Figure 10.

5.2.4. MSE (Mean Squared Error)

The sum of the squared differences (MSE) between the steganographic and initially acquired images quantifies the difference, or the sum of the squared discrepancies among the matching pixels in the two images. A minor MSE represents that the steganographic image is more similar to the initial image and that the embedded data has less impact on the image quality. It is calculated by using the Eqn. (5).

$$MSE = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2 \quad (5)$$

Figure 11: Comparison of MSE

The proposed BFBSA model achieves the lowest MSE value, indicating its superior ability to maintain data fidelity during encryption. Distinctive performance disparities emerge when assessing the Mean Squared Error among several models. BBIPS, DCIEA, and CBIE exhibit significantly higher MSE values of 497.79, 943.34, and 462.609, respectively, suggesting more significant discrepancies between predicted and actual values. However, the proposed BFBSA model demonstrates a substantially lower MSE of 104.6, showcasing its exceptional accuracy. Compared to the other models, BFBSA stands out for its exact outcomes, signifying its superiority in minimizing and delivering highly accurate predictions, thereby establishing itself as a robust and reliable model. The comparison of MSE is depicted in Figure 11.

5.3. Discussion

The proposed model, BFBSA, demonstrates noteworthy efficiency in terms of encryption time and memory consumption. The ability of the models to encrypt data quickly and efficiently while maintaining data quality highlights their effectiveness for secure data transmission and storage. Table 6.6 displays the suggested model's overall performance.

Table 6: Performance assessment

Model Name	BFBSA
Payload Capacity	1399105.125bits
Encryption Time	3.02s
Computation time	37.28s
speed	372.408s
PSNR	55.29db
MSE	104

Based on these metrics, BFBSA is a model that can efficiently handle large volumes of data with relatively good performance in encryption and memory usage.

6. CONCLUSION

The introduction of the novel BFBSA tailored explicitly for the IoT healthcare environment showcases promising results in this study. BFBSA was validated through a comprehensive process involving encryption, embedding healthcare image data, and subsequent performance evaluation based on crucial metrics. The findings underline BFBSA's commendable performance in encryption time and memory consumption, essential factors in secure data handling. Its ability to swiftly encrypt data without compromising quality establishes its suitability for ensuring secure transmission and storage of sensitive healthcare information in IoT environments. The payload capacity earned by our proposed technique is 1399105.125. when compared to the existing methods, payload capacity, PSNR, MSE, values improved. Future work could further enhance the BFBSA algorithm's effectiveness by exploring different encryption methods and optimization. Additionally, investigating the applicability of the BFBSA algorithm to other types of data, like video and text, would be a valuable area of research.

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